

CURRENCY DETECTION APP FOR VISUALLY IMPAIRED

Rahamath Nisha .M
3rd Bsc
Department of Information technology
Rathinam College of Arts and Science
Coimbatore- 641021

Mrs.A.S.R Sulthana
Assistant professor
Department of Information technology
Rathinam College of Arts and Science
Coimbatore- 641021

Abstract: Apart from the immediate use of Master cards and any form of electronic payment methods, money has been widely used for general exchange due to its usefulness. However, visually impaired people can suffer to know each currency paper separately. This research project aims to develop a mobile application based on the Convolutional Neural Network using pre-trained representations to permit visually impaired people to see Indian banknotes to real time situations. The elementary methods used in our planned system include pre-image classification, segmentation, histogram equalization, Region of Interest (ROI), and finally template matching using MobileNetV1-224 and Tensor Flow. Visually Impaired are those people who have vision impaired in performing daily activities are in great number. They also face a lot of difficulties in monetary transactions. They are unable to recognize the paper currencies due to similarity of paper texture and size between different categories. This money detector app helps visually impaired patients to recognize and detect money. Using this application blind people can speak and give command to open camera of a smartphone and camera will click picture of the note and tell the user by speech how much the money note is. This Android project uses speech to text conversion to convert the command given by the blind patient. Speech Recognition is a technology that allows users to provide spoken input into the systems. This android application uses text value into speech. For currency detection, this application uses Azure custom vision API using Machine learning classifications technique to detect currency based on images or paper using mobile camera.

Keywords: Intelligent System, Indian paper currency, currency recognition, currency model, convolutional neural network, visually impaired users, audio output.

Introduction: A currency detection app for visually impaired people in an application that helps them recognize and detect money notes. Using this application, blind people can speak and give commands to open the camera of the smartphone, and the camera will click a picture of the note and tell the user by speech how much the money note is. This android application uses text-to-speech concept to read the value of note to the user and then it converts the text value into speech. Research work in the domain of image processing is evolving rapidly; specifically in the banking sector. Along with the evolving technologies and the growth of the banking sector; the requirement to precisely and efficiently detect currency and its denomination is also growing in parallel. The World Health Organization (WHO) had a survey over around 285 million people. The statistics showed that among the population under consideration while survey, 39 were visually impaired. So, a desperate need of designing a system that will help these people in recognizing the currency; Shows up.

Therefore, in order to help the visually disabled, they studied different algorithms which can be implemented in a system for detection of Indian currency using image processing. Generally, currency recognition is done by using a camera or any image and the result is

displayed on the screen and also an audio output can be provided. One of the difficulty for people with visual impairment is the inability to identify the paper currencies due to the approximation of paper texture and size between the different types of currencies.

Working: Here is a detailed usage of the components and features in this currency detection application.

- 1.**Capture an image:** This app would use the device camera to capture the image of the banknote.
- 2.**Preprocess the image:** The app would use image processing techniques to enhance the image and remove any background noise or distortion.
- 3.**Detect the banknote:** The app would use object detection techniques to locate the banknote within the image.
- 4.**Extract features:** The app would extract feature from the banknote image, such as the color, size and texture of the banknote.
- 5.**Classify the banknote:** The app would use machine learning algorithms to classify the banknotes based on their features. This app would have been trained on the dataset of banknote images, which would allow it to recognize different denominations of banknotes.
- 6.**Provide feedback:** This app would provide a audio feedback to the user, indicating the denomination of the banknote. The feedback might be in the form of a spoken word or a series of beeps or tones that correspond to different denominations.

Proposed Method: We have two phases: (offline and online). The offline phase in which the dataset is constructed from a given collection of Indian currencies images. The online phase in which the proposed method is running to detect and recognize the unknown input currency image. The online phase has five steps, pre-processing techniques for removing noise and preparing the image for next operations, segmentation and ROI extraction processes in the second and third step for extracting the foreground currency from the background, applying ORB Algorithm in step four and finally matching the results with the dataset. In the last steps, the input to the binary document type will require very little space to get stored.

Segmentation - The processes of partitioning an image or text into parts to make them useful for the image processing functionalities such as feature extraction, recognition, etc., is termed to be known as segmentation.

Feature extraction - The process of extraction of the features that act as essential as well as required characteristics such as symbols, text, etc., is termed to be known as feature extraction.

Recognition - The process of identifying the features after extraction is termed to be known as recognition.

Flowchart:

Figure 1.1

Figure 1.2

Figure 1.3

Figure 1.4

Advantages:

- This android application will help visually impaired to know the value of money.
- Blind people can also call the person from contact by giving commands.

Disadvantages:

- Application requires active internet connection.
- User needs to put correct data or else it will behave abnormally.

Conclusion: This application provides a good support and a clear view for the visually impaired people to know the clear clarification of the banknote. By this application every visually impaired people can recognize the currency notes. As it provides many features, it is very efficient to work and use.

Reference:

1. Ronghua Shang, Yijing Yuan, Licheng Jiao, Biao Hou, Amir M. Ghalamzan E, and Rustam Stolkin – A Fast Algorithm for SAR Image Segmentation Based on Key Pixels -Oct 2017
2. Anwar Wanjara, Priyanka Satija, Nikita Patil, Samiksha Chindhalore, Shubham Gaulkar, Prof. A. D. Gotmare – Counterfeit Currency Detection System
3. Gerrit J. J. van den Burg, Christopher K. I. Williams – An Evaluation of Change Point Detection Algorithms – May 2020
4. Xiaole Zhanga, Yuying Shi a, Zhi-Feng Pangb, Yonggui Zhu – Fast algorithm for image denoising with different boundary conditions
5. Jyothi, Ch Ratna, Y. K. Sundara Krishna, and V. Srinivasa Rao. "Paper currency recognition for colour images based on Artificial Neural Network." In Electrical, Electronics, and Optimization Techniques (ICEEOT), International Conference on, pp. 3402-3406. IEEE, 2016.

Websites:

1. **American Foundation for the Blind:** This website provides information and resources on assistive technology for people with visual impairments, including currency identification apps. They also have a directory of app developers that specialize in assistive technology.
2. **National Federation of the Blind:** The National Federation of the Blind (NFB) provides information and resources on assistive technology for the visually impaired, including currency identification apps. They also have a directory of app developers and vendors that specialize in assistive technology.
3. **Royal National Institute of Blind People:** The Royal National Institute of Blind People (RNIB) is a UK-based organization that provides information and resources for people with visual impairments. Their website includes a section on assistive technology, which includes information on currency identification apps.

4. **AbilityNet:** AbilityNet is a UK-based organization that provides advice and support on assistive technology for people with disabilities. Their website includes information on currency identification apps for the visually impaired.
5. **AppleVis:** AppleVis is a community-powered website that provides information and resources on using Apple products with assistive technology, including currency identification apps. Their website includes reviews and user guides for a variety of apps that are accessible to visually impaired users.